

Employee Motivation, Job Satisfaction, and Performance of City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the interrelationship among employee motivation, job satisfaction, and job performance of City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China. This study aimed in achieving operational effectiveness, particularly within the public sector. The study also investigated the correlations between these variables and developed a strategic action plan aimed at enhancing employee motivation, thereby improving job satisfaction and sustaining high levels of job performance.

Using stratified random sampling, 73 out of 90 qualified respondents participated. A researcher-designed questionnaire, validated by experts and demonstrating high reliability (Cronbach's Alpha > 0.949), served as the main data collection tool. Statistical tools such as frequency distribution, weighted mean, and Pearson's r correlation were employed for analysis. Findings revealed that employee motivation and job satisfaction were both at a "high" level (means of 3.15 and 3.13, respectively), while job performance was rated "very high" (mean = 3.41). Strong positive correlations were found among all three variables, highlighting the interdependent nature of motivation, satisfaction, and performance

Keywords: motivation, job satisfaction, job performance

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, motivation has been conceptualized and interpreted in various ways, leading to the development of several theories aimed at explaining human behavior, needs, and expectations in organizational settings. The evolving demands of modern workplaces compel organizations to reassess and realign their systems, strategies, and cultures to stay competitive. Within this context, organizational culture has emerged as a crucial factor influencing success. Motivation, defined as a set of internal psychological processes that initiate and direct behavior, is central to understanding how employees function within organizations. These processes are shaped by goals, interests, desires, and needs that serve as behavioral incentives (Pungan et al., 2022).

Febrianti et al. (2020) described motivation as a powerful force that energizes and regulates behavior, driving individuals to pursue specific actions. In today's dynamic organizational environment, it is increasingly essential to focus on employee motivation, support, and empowerment. According to Kalogiannidis (2021), employee motivation is vital for achieving growth, development, and sustainability in organizations. This underscores the

responsibility of leaders to implement strategies that boost motivation and, in turn, improve job performance and overall organizational effectiveness. Al Balushi et al. (2020) found that employee motivation significantly influences job satisfaction, with motivated workers more likely to experience fulfillment in their roles. As Engidaw (2021) emphasized, organizations must understand what drives their employees and tailor motivational strategies accordingly. This includes aligning employees' personal goals with the organization's mission to foster greater engagement and commitment.

Job satisfaction, according to Gun et al. (2021), refers to individuals' emotional responses toward their job and its various elements. It is a subjective construct shaped by the alignment between job expectations, organizational attributes, and working conditions. Putra et al. (2022) noted that while definitions may vary, terms such as job satisfaction, employee satisfaction, and workplace well-being are often used interchangeably to describe how content or fulfilled employees feel in their roles. Tiwari et al. (2023) added that job satisfaction significantly influences employees' attitudes and work performance.

Forson et al. (2021) defined job performance as behavior directed toward achieving goals, accompanied by evaluative components. Many studies highlight the impact of autonomous and intrinsic motivation on performance, arguing that motivated employees tend to exhibit higher productivity and dedication. Mesiya (2019) reiterated that employee performance is foundational to organizational success, with high-performing employees playing a crucial role in achieving institutional goals.

This research seeks to assess the levels of employee motivation, job satisfaction, and job performance among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China. It further aims to determine the relationships among these variables and to formulate an action plan to enhance employee motivation and satisfaction, thereby sustaining high performance. The study is expected to contribute meaningfully to local government management practices and improve overall service delivery.

METHODS

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to assess the levels of employee motivation, job satisfaction, and performance among City Treasury Bureau. Descriptive research, according to Copeland (2022), aims to characterize the attributes of a particular phenomenon or group. Correlational research, meanwhile, examines the relationships between variables using statistical analysis without manipulating any conditions. By combining both approaches, this study provides a detailed snapshot of the state of motivation, satisfaction, and performance while exploring the possible interrelationships among these variables. The insights gained may guide future interventions and managerial decisions in similar public-sector settings.

The study population consisted of 90 employees from the City Treasury Bureau in Chengdu, China. A sample of 73 respondents was determined using Slovin's formula with a

95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. The respondents were selected through random sampling to ensure fairness and representativeness. The study was conducted during the Academic Year 2024–2025.

To gather the necessary primary data, the researcher developed a self-made questionnaire, structured into three sections: Part I measured the level of employee motivation, Part II measured the level of job satisfaction, and Part III assessed the level of job performance. To ensure content validity, the instrument was reviewed by a panel of experts composed of a researcher, statistician, and subject matter specialist. Their comments and recommendations were incorporated into the final draft. Reliability testing was then conducted using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding the following coefficients:

- Motivation: 0.945
- Satisfaction: 0.949
- Performance: 0.941

These values indicate high reliability, confirming that the questionnaire was consistent and dependable.

Since the questionnaire was self-made, Permission to conduct the study was secured from the Dean of the Graduate School and the research adviser. After the questionnaire was finalized and approved, the researcher personally distributed the survey forms to the selected respondents from the City Treasury Bureau in Chengdu, China.

During distribution, the purpose of the study was clearly explained, and confidentiality of responses was assured. Respondents were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, and assistance was provided for any clarifications. Follow-ups were conducted when necessary to ensure a high response rate. Completed surveys were collected, reviewed, and encoded into a database for analysis. The data were then forwarded to a statistician for processing and interpretation using appropriate statistical techniques.

There are two statistical tools that were used for the quantitative analysis in this study. First, Weighted Mean was used to determine the (a) Employee Motivation, (b) Job Satisfaction and (c) Job Performance of employees from the City Treasury Bureau in Chengdu, China. Next is Pearson r was used to test for significant relationships between the (a) Employee Motivation and Job Satisfaction, (b) Employee Motivation and Job Performance, and (c) Job Satisfaction and Job Performance.

To determine the level of motivation, level of job satisfaction, and level of performance, the following measures were utilized: Strongly Agree (3.25-4.00), Agree (2.50-3.24), Disagree (1.75-2.49) and Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.74).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Discussion of the The Level of Employee Motivation, Level of Job Satisfaction, Level of Job Performance among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China and relationship between them is presented in the succeeding tables and textual presentations.

Table 1 The Level of Employee Motivation among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The work environment in the Treasury Department is conducive to efficiency and collaboration.	3.10	High (Agree)	7
2. The immediate supervisor/s provide/s constructive feedback and support when needed.	3.36	Very High (Strongly Agree)	1
3. Felt recognized and appreciated for the contribution to the Treasury Department.	3.00	High (Agree)	9.5
4. Believe there are enough opportunities and advancement in the current position.	3.12	High (Agree)	6
5. The Treasury Department offers fair and competitive compensation and benefit packages.	3.07	High (Agree)	8
6. Felt motivated to perform at best role within the Treasury Department.	3.22	High (Agree)	3
7. Felt the valued and respected by colleagues and supervisors.	3.16	High (Agree)	4
8. The skills and abilities are utilized in the current role.	3.27	Very High (Strongly Agree)	2
9. Received adequate support and resources to fulfill job responsibilities.	3.15	High (Agree)	5
10. Satisfied with the level of motivation in the work as a Treasury personnel.	3.00	High (Agree)	9.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.15	High (Agree)	

The findings revealed that the overall level of employee motivation among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China was high, with an average weighted mean of 3.15. This suggests that employees generally feel motivated in their roles and perceive their work environment, supervisory support, and opportunities for growth positively. Among the indicators, the highest rating was given to the provision of constructive feedback and support from supervisors, which indicates the value employees place on effective leadership and guidance. The utilization of employees’ skills and abilities was also rated very high, showing that personnel feel their competencies are being maximized in their current roles. Meanwhile, indicators related to recognition, motivation, and overall satisfaction with their motivational state received relatively lower—yet still positive—ratings.

These results align with the views of Kalogiannidis (2021) and Engidaw (2021), who emphasized that motivation is essential for fostering organizational growth and enhancing employee contributions. Furthermore, the importance of aligning individual aspirations with organizational goals, as discussed by Jain et al. (2019), is reflected in the relatively strong motivation levels observed in this study.

Table 2 The Level of Job Satisfaction among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Satisfied with the opportunities for career advancement within the Treasury Department.	3.10	High (Agree)	7
2. Workload is reasonable and manageable.	3.12	High (Agree)	5.5
3. Job allows for a healthy work-life balance.	3.05	High (Agree)	8
4. The Treasury Department provides adequate training and development opportunities to enhance job skills.	3.03	High (Agree)	9
5. Being recognized for the contributions as a Treasury personnel is essential for the job satisfaction.	3.29	Very High (Strongly Agree)	1
6. The Treasury Department promotes a positive work environment conducive to productivity and collaboration.	2.99	High (Agree)	10
7. Achieving success in the roles as a Treasury personnel brings personal satisfaction and fulfillment.	3.25	Very High (Strongly Agree)	2
8. Satisfied with the extent to which talent and expertise are being utilized.	3.12	High (Agree)	5.5
9. Find the work meaningful and fulfilling.	3.22	High (Agree)	3
10. Satisfied with the job in the Treasury Department.	3.16	High (Agree)	4
Average Weighted Mean	3.13	High (Agree)	

The data indicated that the job satisfaction level among City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China is also high, with an average weighted mean of 3.13. This reflects that most employees are content with various aspects of their jobs, such as workload manageability, career advancement opportunities, and the overall meaning and fulfillment derived from their roles.

The highest-rated indicator was recognition for contributions, emphasizing the significance of acknowledgment in promoting satisfaction. Personal fulfillment, meaningful

work, and general job satisfaction also received high ratings, demonstrating that intrinsic aspects of the job contribute greatly to overall satisfaction. Indicators that received the lowest ratings, while still interpreted as high, were related to training opportunities and the promotion of a productive work environment, suggesting areas for potential improvement.

These results resonate with Gun et al. (2021) and Licudan-Credo & Naparota (2022), who emphasized the emotional and psychological factors contributing to job satisfaction, such as recognition, fulfillment, and alignment between job expectations and experiences.

Table 3 The Level of Job Performance among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Consistently meet the performance expectation set for role in the Treasury Department	3.40	Very High (Strongly Agree)	7.5
2. Confident in the ability to perform the tasks and responsibilities assigned in the Treasury Department.	3.51	Very High (Strongly Agree)	1
3. Maintain a high level of accuracy and attention to detail in work.	3.40	Very High (Strongly Agree)	7.5
4. Demonstrate a strong work ethic and commitment to achieving departmental goals.	3.41	Very High (Strongly Agree)	5
5. Effectively prioritize tasks to ensure timely completion of work assignments	3.41	Very High (Strongly Agree)	5
6. Effectively communicate and collaborate with colleagues to accomplish shared objectives.	3.41	Very High (Strongly Agree)	5
7 Feel determined to do best work every day.	3.44	Very High (Strongly Agree)	3
8. Believe if perform well in the role as a Treasury personnel, it will lead to positive recognition from supervisors.	3.34	Very High (Strongly Agree)	9
9. The feedback receives about the job performance as a Treasury personnel influences the-commitment to improving.	3.32	Very High (Strongly Agree)	10
10. Satisfied with job performance in the Treasury Department.	3.47	Very High (Strongly Agree)	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.41	Very High (Strongly Agree)	

Based on the responses, the job performance of City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China was assessed as very high, with an average weighted mean of 3.41. This

finding implies that employees consistently meet or exceed performance expectations and demonstrate confidence, accountability, and reliability in fulfilling their job responsibilities.

High ratings were particularly observed in areas such as confidence in task execution, meeting deadlines, and demonstrating accountability. These reflect strong professional standards and a proactive approach to task completion. The relatively lower scores—though still high—were given to indicators involving adaptability to challenges and goal achievement, which could be further enhanced through additional support and training.

These findings are consistent with the studies of Mesiya (2019) and Forson et al. (2021), who emphasized that high-performing employees are essential to organizational effectiveness. The strong performance also suggests that motivated and satisfied employees are more likely to display optimal job behavior and output.

Table 4 Relationship between the Level of Employee Motivation and Level of Job Satisfaction among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China

Variables	Pearson r value	p-value	Interpretation
The Level of Employee Motivation and Level of Job Satisfaction among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China	0.816** High correlation	0.000	Significant
**Significant @ 0.01			

As shown in Table 4, the relationship between the Level of Employee Motivation and Level of Job Satisfaction among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China, with a Pearson r value of 0.816, demonstrates a strong correlation. The p-value of 0.000, which is below the significance threshold of 0.01, confirms a statistically significant relationship between these two variables. This suggests that higher levels of employee motivation are associated with higher levels of job satisfaction among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China.

In line with this, Lu and Chen (2022) concluded that: (1) public service motivation significantly and positively influences job satisfaction; (2) work engagement and organizational commitment significantly and positively impact job satisfaction; and (3) work engagement and organizational commitment mediate the relationship between public service motivation and job satisfaction. Similarly, Al Balushi et al. (2020) emphasized the critical role of employee motivation in achieving high levels of satisfaction among workers. Their findings suggest that motivation is key to fostering job satisfaction and is essential for accomplishing organizational goals effectively and efficiently. In today’s business environment, focusing on motivation, support, and encouragement is increasingly important.

Conversely, the study by Nitafan and Camay (2020) found that work motivation among regular employees did not show a significant correlation with job satisfaction. While a weak positive relationship was observed, the correlation was not statistically significant, suggesting that the observed relationship between work motivation and job satisfaction was likely due to chance.

Table 5 Relationship between the Level of Employee Motivation and Level of Job Performance among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China

Variables	Pearson r value	p-value	Interpretation
The Level of Employee Motivation and Level of Job Performance among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China	0.525** Moderate correlation	0.000	Significant
**Significant @ 0.01			

As shown in Table 5, the relationship between the Level of Employee Motivation and Level of Job Performance among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China, with a Pearson r value of 0.525, indicates a moderate correlation. A p-value of 0.000, which is below the 0.01 significance level, demonstrates a statistically significant relationship between the Level of Employee Motivation and Level of Job Performance among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China. This suggests that higher levels of employee motivation are associated with higher levels of job performance among the personnel.

The findings of this study align with those of Manzoor et al. (2021), who found that intrinsic rewards significantly enhance employee motivation and performance. Additionally, their study showed that employee motivation positively mediates the relationship between intrinsic rewards and employee performance. It is widely believed that motivated employees exhibit improved performance. This implies that organizations with effective reward management systems can expect increased motivation and performance among their employees. Kumari et al. (2021) also highlighted that their research showed motivation has a significant positive impact on employee job performance, emphasizing its role in improving employee efficiency and productivity, thereby enhancing both individual and organizational capabilities to achieve desired goals.

Elvina and Chao (2019) further noted that work motivation is crucial in any organizational setting, with organizations implementing various motivation strategies to improve employee performance for better outcomes. Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation are considered the most influential factors in enhancing organizational performance. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a strong positive relationship between work motivation and employee performance.

Table 6 Relationship between the Level of Job Satisfaction and Level of Job Performance among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China

Variables	Pearson r value	p-value	Interpretation
The Level of Job Satisfaction and Level of Job Performance among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China	0.577** Moderate correlation	0.000	Significant
**Significant @ 0.01			

As shown in Table 6, the relationship between the Level of Job Satisfaction and Level of Job Performance among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China, with a Pearson r value of 0.577, indicates a moderate correlation. A p-value of 0.000, which is lower than the 0.01 significance level, demonstrates a statistically significant relationship between these two variables. This suggests that as job satisfaction increases, job performance among the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China also increases.

The findings of this study align with those of Gun et al. (2021), whose Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) results supported the hypothesis that job satisfaction positively affects job performance. Their study indicated that as job satisfaction increases, so does job performance. Similarly, the analysis by Rodrigo et al. (2022) concluded that job satisfaction has a significant positive impact on employee performance, with their results consistent with past research. Additionally, they suggested that future studies could explore how leadership and organizational culture influence employee performance, contributing to existing theories on the subject. Furthermore, Ertekin (2021) conducted a study in the sports industry and found a positive relationship between job satisfaction and job performance. His research concluded that as job performance in the sports industry increases, job satisfaction also rises in parallel.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China are generally well-motivated and express satisfaction in their roles, indicating a conducive work environment that encourages employee engagement and productivity. Their Performance levels are exceptionally high, implying that employees not only feel supported and valued but also exhibit strong commitment and effectiveness in delivering their duties. Moreover, The positive correlations among the three variables confirm that employee motivation and job satisfaction are strong predictors of job performance. Employees who are motivated and satisfied tend to be more productive, focused, and aligned with organizational goals. Although findings were positive, there is still room for

improvement—particularly in areas such as training opportunities, work-life balance, and creating even more meaningful recognition programs.

The higher the level of employee motivation, the higher the level of job performance of the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China. The higher the level of job satisfaction, the higher the level of job performance of the City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China.

A proposed action plan for implementation to enhance employee motivation and subsequently improving job satisfaction and sustain performance of City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China is necessary to elevate the level of employee motivation which will lead to increased job satisfaction and better performance

The following recommendations are based on findings and conclusion of this study: Enhance motivational strategies by implementing structured recognition programs, leadership development, and clear career advancement pathways to sustain and elevate motivation levels. Foster a more fulfilling work environment by regularly assessing employee satisfaction through feedback mechanisms and aligning employee tasks with their skills, strengths, and aspirations. Provide more targeted training and development opportunities, ensuring that all personnel have access to upskilling and reskilling programs that enhance job performance and personal growth. Maintain strong supervisory support and communication, as these were highly valued by respondents. Managers should continue offering constructive feedback and fostering a culture of mutual respect and collaboration. Implement the proposed action plan developed in the latter part of the study, which outlines steps for improving motivation, sustaining job satisfaction, and maintaining high performance among City Treasury Bureau personnel. Given existing recommendations and action plans in place, the researcher will team up with the HR Department to organize training seminars for City Treasury Bureau Personnel in Chengdu, China, ensuring they align with organizational goals. Feedback from HR will tailor the seminars to address identified areas for improvement, enhancing motivation, job satisfaction, and performance in City Governments. HR Manager may clearly communicate how the proposed initiatives and activities will enhance employee motivation and subsequently improving job satisfaction and sustain performance of the organization. This involves gaining support from Local Chief Executive to effectively implement action plans that includes strategies like conducting workshop/trainings/seminars related to employee motivation and job satisfaction and promoting work-life balance with recreational programs. It also include allocating resources appropriately to support the implementation of these initiatives and activities.

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